

Appendix D.1. Variables of the HILDA survey

Table D.1: Summary of variables used in the study.

Variable	Description	Type	Observations
Participant ID	Identification of the participant.	—	This variable was not included in the prediction model
Year	Year the participant data was collected.	Discrete	This variable was not included in the prediction model
Part-time employment rate	Percentage of the workforce employed part-time.	Continuous	
Unemployment rate	Total unemployment rate.	Continuous	Reflects shifts in labor market conditions and employment opportunities.
Unemployment rate change	Year-over-year change in the total unemployment rate.	Continuous	
Total labor force participation rate	Labor force participation rate.	Continuous	
Total labor force participation rate change	Year-over-year change in the total labor force participation rate.	Continuous	Indicates changes in the proportion of individuals actively participating in the labor market.
GSP per capita	Gross state product per capita.	Continuous	
GSP per capita growth	Growth rate of gross state product per capita.	Continuous	
GSP per capita growth change	Year-over-year change in the growth rate of gross state product per capita.	Continuous	Captures the economic growth fluctuations at the state level.
Energy price	Energy price.	Continuous	
Energy price change	Year-over-year change in the energy price.	Continuous	Adjusted for inflation. Measures fluctuations in energy costs that may impact household energy affordability.
Years of education	Logarithm of the number of years the participant has been educated.	Continuous	
Age	Age	Discrete	
Married	If married (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Divorced	If divorced (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Widowed	If widowed (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Children presence at household	Number of minors at home.	Discrete	
Unemployment status	If unemployed (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Poor health	If the individual perceives their health status as bad or very bad (=1) or not (=0).	Binary	
Employment status	If employed (=1) or not (=0).	Binary	
Household size	Household size.	Discrete	
Household income	Logarithm of the household income.	Continuous	
Household income change	Year-over-year change in the household income.	Continuous	Reflects income volatility and its potential effect on household vulnerability to energy poverty.
Household region 2 to 8	Various one-hot encoded regional and household state indicators.	Binary (one-hot encoded)	
MEPI	Poverty indicator.	Continuous	Includes the 2M, TPR, LHC indicators, and measures of inability to pay for adequate heating (Heat) or utility bills on time (Arrears).

Appendix D.2. Model selection and grid search parameters

To identify the optimal models and hyperparameter configurations for predicting energy poverty, a grid search approach was implemented. This process systematically tested combinations of model parameters and evaluated their performance using cross-validation.

We used 5-fold cross-validation on the training dataset to ensure that the models were tested on various data splits and that the hyperparameters chosen were robust across different subsets of data. The best set of hyperparameters was then chosen based on the highest average Receiver Operating Characteristic - Area Under Curve (ROC AUC) score from the validation folds. The ROC AUC score measures the model's ability to discriminate between energy-poor and non-energy-poor households.

For all models, the grid search incorporated time window sizes and cut-off points to capture the temporal dynamics of energy poverty predictors. Additionally, the grid search utilized the one-vs-rest framework, which creates a binary classifier for each class.

The grid search was applied to three machine learning models commonly used for imbalanced classification tasks. All models were optimized and trained using Python, and the scikit-learn library for model implementation and evaluation. The models and their corresponding parameter grids are described below.

Appendix D.2.1. Model A: Random under-sampling boost

The random under-sampling boost classifier is an ensemble method that combines boosting with random under-sampling to address class imbalance efficiently. Based on the AdaBoost algorithm, the classifier under-samples the training data during each boosting iteration in order to guarantee an equal representation of the minority (energy-poor) and majority (not energy-poor) classes. Weak classifiers, such as decision trees, are iteratively trained, with misclassified instances receiving higher weights. The final model aggregates predictions from all weak classifiers through weighted voting.

The grid search included the following parameters:

- Number of estimators: 50, 100, 200
- Learning rate: 0.01, 0.1, 1.0
- Algorithm type: SAMME, SAMME.R

- Sampling strategy: Auto, 0.5, 1.0
- Replacement: True, False

Appendix D.2.2. Model B: Easy ensemble

The easy ensemble classifier [LWZ09] works by creating multiple balanced subsets of the training data through under-sampling of the majority class (in the case of this work, the not energy-poor class). For each balanced subset, an AdaBoost learner (which, in this context, uses a decision tree as the base estimator) is trained. The outcomes from all subsets are then combined to form a robust ensemble, and thus, prediction. As a result, the classifier ensures that the model remains sensitive to the energy-poor class (minority) while maintaining robust overall performance.

The grid search explored the following parameters:

- Number of estimators: 10, 50, 100
- Sampling strategy: Auto, 0.5, 1.0
- Replacement: True, False

Appendix D.3. Model C: Balanced bagging

A balanced bagging classifier [GFB⁺12] is an ensemble technique that combines the predictions of multiple base models, e.g., decision trees, in order to improve the robustness and accuracy of the outcomes. This method specifically addresses class imbalance by ensuring that each decision tree in the ensemble is trained on a balanced subset of the dataset. These subsets are created by resampling the original training data, wherein each subset contains a representative distribution of both minority (energy-poor) and majority (not energy-poor) classes.

The parameter grid included the following parameters:

- Number of estimators: 10, 50, 100
- Maximum samples: 0.5, 1.0
- Maximum features: 0.5, 1.0
- Bootstrap sampling: True, False
- Bootstrap feature selection: True, False

Table D.2: Predictive performance of the balanced bagging classifier model across varying time windows (with contemporaneous variables included).

Window size (T)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
2	75.72	75.45	75.59
4	73.48	76.53	75.01
8	70.86	78.54	74.70
12	71.01	78.20	74.61
14	81.89	72.51	77.20

- Sampling strategy: Auto, 0.5, 1.0
- Replacement: True, False

Appendix D.4. Model performance with contemporaneous variables included

To assess the robustness of our main findings, we estimated additional models that incorporate both historical and contemporaneous variables. While the main analysis of this paper emphasizes historical predictors to capture temporal dynamics, this supplementary analysis evaluates whether including contemporaneous information changes model performance or the relevance of historical variables.

Table D.2 presents the predictive performance of the model, as used in the main analysis, across time windows of $T = 2, 4, 8, 12$, and 14 years. As expected, including contemporaneous information improves classification performance across all time windows, as reflected by consistently higher ROC AUC scores.

In most cases, sensitivity and specificity increase with the addition of contemporaneous variables. The only exception is the baseline time window ($T = 8$), where sensitivity decreases slightly from 73.25% to 70.86%, while specificity improves substantially from 66.77% to 78.54%. This trade-off still results in an improvement in the overall model performance.

Adding contemporaneous variables enhances the models' ability to correctly identify households that are not energy-poor while maintaining strong accuracy in detecting those that are. For the baseline time window ($T = 8$), ROC AUC increases from 70.01% to 74.70%, representing a relative gain of 4.69 percentage points. This suggests that while contemporaneous factors contribute with valuable short-term predictive information, long-term so-

Figure D.1: Relative contribution (%) of predictive variables to energy poverty outcomes across an 8-year time window, presented as summed normalized importance (left) and discriminated by period (right).

cioeconomic trajectories remain highly informative and central to identifying energy poverty risk.

On the other hand, Figure D.1 compares the relative importance of predictors for the baseline time window ($T = 8$) in the model that includes both contemporaneous and historical variables. In the left plot, where variables are aggregated regardless of time, household income alone accounts for 42.34% of the total normalized importance. Overall, the order of relative contributions is consistent with the results from the model that included only historical variables.

However, when we disaggregate the importance scores by time (as shown in the right plot), contemporaneous income and income change emerge as the most influential predictors, together accounting for 27.33% of the total accumulated importance. After these two, historical income variables become increasingly important, with their contributions varying by lag. In particular, lagged household income from $T - 1$ through $T - 5$ makes a substantial contribution to the model, exceeding the influence of the contemporaneous income; a similar pattern is observed for the income change variable. Notably, most predictors with a normalized importance of at least 1% are historical. This highlights that, while contemporaneous indicators provide strong immediate signals, historical information also plays an important role in forecasting energy poverty.

Appendix D.5. Model performance across time windows and cut-off value

This appendix presents the performance results of all models tested in the study, evaluated across various cut-off values (\bar{m}) and time windows (T). The results are summarized in terms of sensitivity, specificity and ROC AUC. The best model was selected based on the highest average ROC AUC value, calculated independently of specific cut-off values and time windows. This approach ensures that the chosen model has consistently strong performance across all configurations tested.

Those performance metrics used in this evaluation are briefly described below:

Sensitivity: The percentage of correctly identified energy-poor households among all actual energy-poor households. Higher sensitivity indicates better identification of the minority (energy-poor) class.

Specificity: The percentage of correctly identified non-energy-poor households among all actual non-energy-poor households. Higher specificity reflects fewer false positives.

ROC AUC: (Receiver Operating Characteristic - Area Under Curve)
A measure of the model's overall ability to discriminate between energy-poor and non-energy-poor households across varying thresholds. Higher values indicate better discrimination.

Table D.3: Performance results of models across cutoff values (\hat{m}) and time windows. This table summarizes the sensitivity, specificity, ROC AUC for each model evaluated in the study. The results highlight the impact of varying cutoff values and time windows on model performance.

Model	Cut-off (\hat{m})	Window size (T)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	ROC AUC (%)	Average ROC AUC (%)
Random under-sampling boost	0	2	67.35	67.66	67.50	69.50 \pm 6.22
		4	65.64	68.83	67.24	
		8 (baseline)	68.26	66.77	67.52	
		12	57.40	65.41	61.40	
	0.2	14	65.35	70.08	67.72	69.50 \pm 6.22
		2	69.08	75.09	72.09	
		4	67.97	76.25	72.11	
		8 (baseline)	68.31	75.59	71.95	
	0.4	12	55.81	78.57	67.19	69.50 \pm 6.22
		14	66.67	79.04	72.85	
		2	73.49	78.49	75.99	
		4	74.66	82.32	78.49	
Balanced bagging	0	8 (baseline)	79.55	79.80	79.67	73.22 \pm 4.48
		12	40.00	88.71	64.36	
		14	25.00	87.85	56.43	
		2	70.39	69.23	69.81	
	0.2	4	70.82	73.65	72.24	73.22 \pm 4.48
		8 (baseline)	73.25	66.77	70.01	
		12	71.60	65.79	68.69	
		14	78.74	66.31	72.52	
	0.4	2	74.32	72.43	73.38	73.22 \pm 4.48
		4	77.71	72.81	75.26	
		8 (baseline)	73.94	72.21	73.08	
		12	55.81	85.41	70.61	
Easy ensemble	0	14	85.71	69.60	77.66	70.59 \pm 4.82
		2	74.46	76.50	75.48	
		4	76.71	78.36	77.54	
		8 (baseline)	79.55	74.27	76.91	
	0.2	12	80.00	83.36	81.68	70.59 \pm 4.82
		14	50.00	76.72	63.36	
		2	67.40	67.47	67.43	
		4	66.39	67.37	66.88	
	0.4	8 (baseline)	68.86	65.85	67.35	70.59 \pm 4.82
		12	63.31	62.22	62.77	
		14	69.29	68.19	68.74	
		2	69.63	74.47	72.05	
0.4	4	69.70	76.15	72.92	70.59 \pm 4.82	
	8 (baseline)	71.13	72.09	71.61		
	12	60.47	75.53	68.00		
	14	57.14	84.49	70.81		
0.4	2	74.22	77.85	76.03	70.59 \pm 4.82	
	4	76.03	79.93	77.98		
	8 (baseline)	77.27	77.63	77.45		
	12	40.00	86.40	63.20		
0.4	14	75.00	76.32	75.66	70.59 \pm 4.82	

Appendix D.6. Robustness Check: Income Increases and MEPI

Table D.4: OLS regression of MEPI on small income increase (0–5%), with year fixed effects

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>z</i>-stat	<i>p</i>-value
Intercept	0.0550	0.003	20.034	<0.001
Small income increase (0–5%)	-0.0112	0.002	-6.282	<0.001
Year fixed effects	Yes			
Observations		64,927		

Results are based on OLS regression with robust standard errors clustered by household. Households experiencing a modest year-to-year income increase of less than 5% exhibit a lower average MEPI (0.051) compared to households without such an increase (0.062). Regression results confirm that these differences are statistically significant.

A small income increase is associated with an average reduction in MEPI of 0.011 ($p < 0.001$), even after controlling for year fixed effects and clustering standard errors at the household level.

These findings support the plausibility of our counterfactual scenarios by showing that the small income changes highlighted by the framework correspond to realistic and observed transitions in the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) dataset.

References

- [GFB⁺12] Mikel Galar, Alberto Fernandez, Edurne Barrenechea, Humberto Bustince, and Francisco Herrera. A review on ensembles for the class imbalance problem: Bagging-, boosting-, and hybrid-based approaches. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, 42(4):463–484, 2012.
- [LWZ09] Xu-Ying Liu, Jianxin Wu, and Zhi-Hua Zhou. Exploratory undersampling for class-imbalance learning. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)*, 39(2):539–550, 2009.

Appendix D.7. Variables of the HILDA survey

Table D.5: Summary of variables used in the study.

Variable	Description	Type	Observations
Participant ID	Identification of the participant.	—	
Year	Year the participant data was collected.	Discrete	
Part-time employment rate	Percentage of the workforce employed part-time.	Continuous	
Unemployment rate	Total unemployment rate.	Continuous	
Total labor force participation rate	Labor force participation rate.	Continuous	
GSP per capita	Gross state product per capita.	Continuous	
GSP per capita growth	Growth rate of gross state product per capita.	Continuous	
Energy price	Energy price.	Continuous	Adjusted for inflation.
Years of education	Logarithm of the number of years the participant has been educated.	Continuous	
Age	Age	Discrete	
Sex	Sex	Discrete	
Married	If married (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Divorced	If divorced (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Widowed	If widowed (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Single	If single (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Children presence at household	Number of minors at home.	Discrete	
Unemployment status	If unemployed (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Remoteness	If the individual lives in a remote area (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Household income	Logarithm of the household income.	Continuous	
Social capital	Level of participant's social networks and community ties.	Continuous	
Inactive	If the individual is inactive (=1) or not (=0)	Binary	
Employment status	If employed (=1) or not (=0).	Binary	
Household region 2 to 8	Various one-hot encoded regional and household state indicators.	Binary (one-hot encoded)	
Health stock	Individual's health status	Continuous	Involves a GOP estimation where SAH is specified as a function of detailed physical health indicators.
MEPI	Poverty indicator.	Continuous	Includes the 2M, TPR, LHC indicators, and measures of inability to pay for adequate heating (Heat) or utility bills on time (Arrears).